

Fitting of data: JBW-NP-P-5NM-V3 2021-02-18_11-10-43
 $0.0201 \leq q \text{ (nm}^{-1}\text{)} \leq 23.8$
Active parameters: 1, ranges: 1
Background level: 0.0122 ± 0.000479
(Scaling factor: $1.41\text{e}+33 \pm 2.78\text{e}+30$)
Timing: 10 repetitions of 376 ± 137 seconds

Range $1.500\text{e}-10$ to $1.500\text{e}-07$, vol-weighted
totalValue: $1.360\text{e}-03 \pm 1.875\text{e}-06$
mean: $5.327\text{e}-09 \pm 4.206\text{e}-12$
variance: $4.544\text{e}-18 \pm 1.187\text{e}-19$
skew: $3.373\text{e}+00 \pm 3.724\text{e}-01$
kurtosis: $3.884\text{e}+01 \pm 6.849\text{e}+00$

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